

Subclass of Bi-Univalent Functions Associated With q -Lommel Polynomials

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Abstract

This study uses the notion of the q -differential operator associated with q -Lommel polynomials to explain new subclass of bi-univalent functions. Additionally, we determine constraints for the initial Taylor-Maclaurin coefficients and initial Fekete-Sezgo inequalities for this recently specified subclass.

Keywords: Bi-Univalent function; starlike function; convex function; q -differential operator; q -Lommel polynomials.

1. Introduction

Let \mathbb{C} be the complex plane and $\mathbb{D} = \{l \in \mathbb{C} : |l| < 1\}$ be open unit disk in \mathbb{C} . Also, let \mathcal{A} denote the class of all analytic functions of the form

$$f(l) = l + a_2 l^2 + a_3 l^3 + \dots = l + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n l^n; l \in \mathbb{D} \quad (1)$$

normalized by $f(0) = f'(0) - 1 = 0$ in the open unit disk \mathbb{D} . The class S is a subclass of \mathcal{A} , said to be univalent functions in \mathbb{D} . In the domain \mathbb{D} , function $f(l)$ is univalent if it satisfies one-one mapping such that for $l_1 \neq l_2$ in \mathbb{D} , $f(l_1) \neq f(l_2)$ exists.

For two functions $f_1(l)$ and $f_2(l) \in \mathbb{D}$, we say $f_1(l)$ is subordinate to $f_2(l)$ if there Schwarz function w exists in \mathbb{D} which is analytic with $|w(z)| < 1$ and $w(0) = 0$, such that $f_1(l) = f_2(w(l))$. This subordination is defined by $f_1 < f_2$ or $f_1(l) < f_2(l), l \in \mathbb{D}$. It is commonly known that, if the $f_2(l)$ is univalent in \mathbb{D} , then (see [10])

$$f_1(l) < f_2(l), l \in \mathbb{D} \Leftrightarrow f_1(0) = f_2(0) \text{ and } f_1(\mathbb{D}) \subset f_2(\mathbb{D}).$$

A domain is considered starlike with respect to a point $w_0 \in \mathbb{D}$ if the line segment connecting any two points in \mathbb{D} to w_0 lies within \mathbb{D} , whereas if the line segment connecting any two points in \mathbb{D} lies wholly in \mathbb{D} then $\mathbb{D} \subset \mathbb{C}$ is convex. If $f(\mathbb{D})$ is a starlike domain with regard to the origin, then a function $f \in \mathcal{A}$ is starlike; if $f(\mathbb{D})$ is convex, then it is convex.

In analytical term, $f \in \mathcal{A}$ is classified as starlike if and only if

$$\operatorname{Re} \left(\frac{lf'(l)}{f(l)} \right) > 0 \quad (l \in \mathbb{D}).$$

The class of starlike functions, commonly referred to as \mathcal{ST} , can be described through the concept of subordination as follows:

$$\mathcal{ST} = \left\{ f \in \mathcal{A} : \frac{lf'(l)}{f(l)} < \frac{1+l}{1-l} \right\},$$

whereas $f \in \mathcal{A}$ is convex if and only if and only if

$$\operatorname{Re} \left(1 + \frac{lf''(l)}{f'(l)} \right) > 0 \quad (l \in \mathbb{D}).$$

A familiar class of convex functions denoted as \mathcal{CV} . This subordination can be expressed as follows:

$$\mathcal{CV} = \left\{ f \in \mathcal{A} : 1 + \frac{lf''(l)}{f'(l)} < \frac{1+l}{1-l} \right\}.$$

Also, Ma and Minda [9] introduced new function $\psi(l)$ by using the concept of subordination will belong to the class \mathcal{P} if

$$\psi(l) = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n l^n, \quad (l \in \mathbb{D}),$$

where $\operatorname{Re}(\psi(l)) > 0$ with $\psi(0) = 1, \psi'(0) > 0$ and for $n \in \mathbb{N}$. They defined $\mathcal{ST}(\psi)$ and $\mathcal{CV}(\psi)$ in the following way:

$$f(l) \in \mathcal{ST}(\psi) \Leftrightarrow \frac{lf'(l)}{f(l)} < \psi(l)$$

and

$$f(l) \in \mathcal{CV}(\psi) \Leftrightarrow 1 + \frac{lf''(l)}{f'(l)} < \psi(l).$$

Every $f \in \mathcal{ST}$ function guarantees that the image of the unit disk consists a disk of radius $1/4$ as stated by/in the Koebe One-Quarter Theorem [3]. Consequently, there is an inverse f^{-1} for every univalent function, its inverse is described as

$$f^{-1}(f(l)) = l, \quad (l \in \mathbb{D})$$

and

$$f(f^{-1}(w)) = w, \quad \left(|w| < r_0(f), r_0(f) \geq \frac{1}{4} \right).$$

The inverse function $g = f^{-1}$ has the form

$$g = f^{-1} = w - (a_2)w^2 + (2a_2^2 - a_3)w^3 - (5a_2^3 - 5a_2a_3 + a_4)w^4 + \dots \quad (2)$$

A function $f \in \mathcal{A}$ is considered bi-univalent in domain \mathbb{D} if both functions f and f^{-1} are univalent in \mathbb{D} . The class of bi-univalent functions in \mathbb{D} is denoted by Σ . The functions f_1, f_2 and f_3 are the examples of the families of Σ which are defined as

$$f_1(l) = l(1 - l)^{-1}, f_2(l) = -\log(1 - l) \text{ and } f_3(l) = \frac{1}{2} \log \frac{1+l}{1-l},$$

with inverse functions

$$g_1(w) = w(1 + w)^{-1}, g_2(w) = \frac{e^w - 1}{e^w} \text{ and } g_3(w) = \frac{e^{2w} - 1}{e^{2w} + 1}.$$

However, the famous Koebe function is not a member of Σ . Also $l - \frac{l^2}{2}$ and $\frac{l}{1-l^2}$ not the member of Σ . Lewin [7] introduced the bi-univalent class Σ and proved that $|a_2| < 1.51$. After that Brannan and Clunie [2] showed that $|a_2| \leq \sqrt{2}$. Subsequently, Netanyahu [10] proved that $\max|a_2| = 4/3$. The exploration of the bi-univalent function class and analytic has actually been greatly enhanced and revitalized by [13] in their pioneering work (also see, [5], [6], [12], [14]).

In class \mathcal{ST} a function's n th coefficient is constrained by n , and the coefficients bounds provide insights into geometric properties of the function. The well-known problem Fekete-Sezgo [4] is to resolute the greatest possible value for the coefficient functional $|a_3 - \mu a_2^2|$ through the class \mathcal{ST} where $\mu \in [0,1]$, solved using the Loewner approach and is presented as follows:

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \begin{cases} 3 - 4\mu & \text{if } \mu \leq 0 \\ 1 + 2\exp\left(\frac{2\mu}{\mu - 1}\right) & \text{if } 0 \leq \mu < 1 \\ 4\mu - 3 & \text{if } \mu \geq 1. \end{cases}$$

Numerous scholars have recently carefully examined a number of noteworthy findings pertaining to the subclass of analytic functions and q operators ([8],[11],[14],[15]).

Definition 1.1. For $0 < q < 1$, the q -derivative of a $f(l)$ is defined as

$$D_q(l) = \begin{cases} \frac{f(ql) - f(l)}{(q - 1)l} & \text{for } l \neq 0 \\ f'(l) & \text{for } l = 0. \end{cases}$$

Remember that $\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} D_q(l) = f'(l)$. From (1) we deduce that,

$$D_q f(l) = 1 + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} [k]_q a^k l^{k-1}, \tag{3}$$

where

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} [k]_q = \frac{1 - q^k}{1 - q} = 1 + q + \dots + q^{k-1} \rightarrow k.$$

Definition 1.2. The expansion defined in the form of

$$(x + a)_q^n = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} q^{\frac{j(j-1)}{2}} \binom{n}{j} a^j x^{n-j}, \tag{4}$$

is known as q -binomial expansion, where $\binom{n}{j}$ is q -binomial coefficient

$$\binom{n}{j} = \frac{[n]_q!}{[j]_q! [n-j]_q!}. \tag{5}$$

Al-Salam and Ismail [1] used the q -Lommel polynomials and give a new q -polynomials as follows

Definition 1.3. [1] The polynomial

$$K_n(x, \alpha, \xi) = \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{n}{2}} \frac{(-\alpha; q) \cdot (q; q)_{n-j} x^{n-2j} (-\xi)^j}{(-\alpha; q) \cdot (q; q)_j (q; q)_{n-j}} q^{j(j-1)}, \tag{6}$$

is known as generalized q -Lommel polynomials.

Theorem 1.1. [1] The generalized q -Lommel polynomials satisfy

$$k_{n+1}(x; \alpha, \xi) = k_n(x; \alpha, \xi)(1 + \alpha q^n)x - k_{n-1}(x; \alpha, \xi)\xi q^{n-1}, \tag{7}$$

with initial condition

$$k_0(x; \alpha, \xi) = 1 \text{ and } k_1(x; \alpha, \xi) = (1 + \alpha)x.$$

Using the generalized q -Lommel polynomials, we establish the following:

Definition 1.4.: Let $\psi(x, l, \alpha, \xi, q)$ be defined as follows

$$\psi(x, l, \alpha, \xi, q) = 1 + \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} k_j(x, l, \alpha, \xi, q) l^j. \tag{8}$$

Nowadays, q -orthogonal polynomials are used extensively in geometric function theory. We present following subclass of bi-univalent functions and analytic using the q -starlike function and the subordination principle:

Definition 1.5. The subclass $\mathcal{F}_{\Sigma}^q(x, \alpha, \xi)$ contains a function $f(l)$ of the form (1), if

$$\frac{l \partial_q f(l)}{f(l)} + \xi \frac{l^2 \partial_q (\partial_q f(l))}{f(l)} < \psi(x, l, \alpha, \xi, q) \left(\frac{1}{2} < x < 1, 0 < q < 1, l \in \mathbb{D} \right)$$

and

$$\frac{\omega \partial_q f(w)}{f(w)} + \xi \frac{w^2 \partial_q (\partial_q f(w))}{f(w)} < \psi(x, w, \alpha, \xi, q) \left(\frac{1}{2} < x < 1, 0 < q < 1, w \in \mathbb{D} \right). \tag{9}$$

By using (7), we found the following relations:

$$k_1(x: \alpha, \xi) = (1 + \alpha)x; k_2(x: \alpha, \xi) = x^2(1 + \alpha q)(x + \alpha) - \xi. \tag{10}$$

We note from (8) that

$$\psi(l, x, \alpha, \xi, q) = 1 + k_1(l, x, \alpha, \xi, q)z + k_2(l, x, \alpha, \xi, q)z^2 + k_3(l, x, \alpha, \xi, q)z^3 + \dots \tag{11}$$

We need the following result to support our main finding.

Lemma 1.1. [9] If $\Phi(l) = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} c_n l^n = 1 + c_1 l + c_2 l^2 + c_3 l^3 + \dots$,

where $\Phi(l)$ belongs to the class \mathcal{P} of functions having positive real root.

Then $|c_n| \leq 2, (n \in \mathbb{N})$. This inequality is sharp for each n .

2. Coefficients Bounds

Theorem 2.1. Let f given by (1) be in the class $\mathcal{F}_{\Sigma}^q(x, \alpha, \xi)$. Then

$$|a_2| \leq \left\{ \frac{x(1 + \alpha)(\sqrt{x(1 + \alpha)})}{\sqrt{x^2(1 + \alpha)^2[\eta_1 - \eta_2] - [\eta_2 - 1]^2[x^2(1 + \alpha q)(1 + \alpha) - \xi - x(1 + \alpha)]}} \right\}$$

and

$$|a_3| \leq \frac{x^2(1 + \alpha)^2}{[(1 + \xi)[2]_q - 1]^2} + \frac{x(1 + \alpha)}{[[3]_q(1 + \xi[2]_q) - 1]}, \tag{12}$$

where $\eta_1 = [3]_q(1 + \xi[2]_q), \eta_2 = (1 + \xi)[2]_q$.

Proof. Since $f(l) \in \mathcal{F}_{\Sigma}^q(x, \alpha, \xi)$, we have

$$\frac{l\partial_q f(l)}{f(l)} + \xi \frac{l^2\partial_q(\partial_q f(l))}{f(l)} = \psi(m(l), x; \alpha, \xi, q) \tag{13}$$

and

$$\frac{\omega\partial_q f(w)}{f(w)} + \xi \frac{w^2\partial_q(\partial_q f(w))}{f(w)} = \psi(n(w), x; \alpha, \xi, q) \tag{14}$$

Let $m, n \in S$, we have

$$m(l) = \frac{1 + \tau(l)}{1 - \tau(l)} = 1 + m_1 l + m_2 l^2 + m_3 l^3 + \dots \tag{15}$$

and

$$\tau(l) = \frac{m(l)-1}{m(l)+1}, l \in \mathbb{D}.$$

For $n(w)$, we have

$$n(w) = \frac{1 + \varepsilon(w)}{1 - \varepsilon(w)} = 1 + n_1w + n_2w^2 + n_3w^3 + \dots, \tag{16}$$

where

$$\varepsilon(\omega) = \frac{n(\omega)-1}{n(\omega)+1}, \omega \in \mathbb{D}.$$

These forms suggest that $m(l)$ and $n(w)$ are power series expansions around $l = 0$ and $w = 0$, respectively. From (15) and (16), we get

$$\tau(l) = \frac{m(l) - 1}{m(l) + 1} = \frac{1}{2} \left[m_1l + \left(m_2 - \frac{m_1^2}{2} \right) l^2 + \left(m_3 - m_1m_2 + \frac{m_1^3}{4} \right) l^3 + \dots \right] \tag{17}$$

and

$$\varepsilon(w) = \frac{n(w) - 1}{n(w) + 1} = \frac{1}{2} \left[n_1w + \left(n_2 - \frac{n_1^2}{2} \right) w^2 + \left(n_3 - n_1n_2 + \frac{n_1^3}{4} \right) w^3 + \dots \right]. \tag{18}$$

From (17) and (18), applying $\psi(m(l), x; \alpha, \xi, q), \psi(n(\omega), x; \alpha, \xi, q)$ given by q -Lommel polynomials, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(\tau(l), x; \alpha, \xi, q) &= 1 + \frac{k_1(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{2} m_1l \\ &+ \left[\frac{k_1(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{2} \left(m_2 - \frac{m_1^2}{2} \right) + \frac{k_2(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{4} m_1^2 \right] l^2 \\ &+ \left\{ \frac{k_1(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{2} \left(m_3 - m_1m_2 + \frac{m_1^3}{4} \right) \right\} l^3 + \dots \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(\varepsilon(\omega), x; \alpha, \xi, q) &= 1 + \frac{k_1(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{2} n_1w \\ &+ \left[\frac{k_1(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{2} \left(n_2 - \frac{n_1^2}{2} \right) + \frac{k_2(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{4} n_1^2 \right] w^2 \\ &+ \left\{ \frac{k_1(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{2} \left(n_3 - n_1n_2 + \frac{n_1^3}{4} \right) + \frac{k_2(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{2} n_1 \left(n_2 - \frac{n_1^2}{2} \right) \right\} w^3 + \dots. \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

From (13), (19), (14) and (20), we have

$$[(1 + \xi)[2]_q - 1]a_2 = \frac{k_1(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{2} m_1, \tag{21}$$

$$[3]q(1 + \xi[2]_q) - 1a_3 - [(1 + \xi)[2]_q - 1]a_2^2 = \frac{k_1(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{2} \left(m_2 - \frac{m_1^2}{2} \right) + \frac{k_2(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{4} m_1^2, \tag{22}$$

$$-[(1 + \xi)[2]_q - 1]a_2 = \frac{k_1(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{2}n_1 \tag{23}$$

and

$$[[3]_q(1 + \xi[2]_q) - 1](2a_2^2 - a_3) - [(1 + \xi)[2]_q - 1]a_2^2 = \frac{k_1(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{2}\left(n_2 - \frac{n_1^2}{2}\right) + \frac{k_2(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{4}n_1^2. \tag{24}$$

Using (21) and (23), we get

$$m_1 = -n_1; m_1^2 = n_1^2; m_1^3 = -n_1^3 \tag{25}$$

and

$$a_2^2 = \frac{k_1^2(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{8[(1 + \xi)[2]_q - 1]^2}(m_1^2 + n_1^2). \tag{26}$$

By using equation (25) and (26), we obtain

$$\frac{2a_2^2[(1 + \xi)[2]_q - 1]^2}{k_1^2(x, \alpha, \xi, q)} = \frac{n_1^2}{2}. \tag{27}$$

By adding (22), (24) and using (25), (26) we have

$$a_2^2 = \frac{k_1^3(x, \alpha, \xi, q)(m_2 + n_2)}{4k_1^2(x, \alpha, \xi, q)[[3]_q(1 + \xi[2]_q) - (1 + \xi)[2]_q] - 4(k_2(x, \alpha, \xi, q) - k_1(x, \alpha, \xi, q))[(1 + \xi)[2]_q - 1]^2}. \tag{28}$$

By using Lemma 1.1, $|m_i| \leq 2$ and $|n_i| \leq 2$ and by result of q -Lommel Polynomials, we have

$$|a_2| \leq \left\{ \frac{x(1 + \alpha)(\sqrt{x(1 + \alpha)})}{\sqrt{x^2(1 + \alpha)^2[\eta_1 - \eta_2] - [\eta_2 - 1]^2[x^2(1 + \alpha q)(1 + \alpha) - \xi - x(1 + \alpha)]}} \right\}, \tag{29}$$

where $\eta_1 = [3]_q(1 + \xi[2]_q), \eta_2 = (1 + \xi)[2]_q$.

Now by subtracting (24) from (22) and using (25), we get

$$2a_3[[3]_q(1 + \xi[2]_q) - 1] - [[3]_q(1 + \xi[2]_q) - 1]2a_2^2 = \frac{k_1(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{2}(m_2 - n_2). \tag{30}$$

Using (26) and Lemma 1.1, $|m_i| \leq 2$ and $|n_i| \leq 2$, we have

$$|a_3| \leq \frac{x^2(1 + \alpha)^2}{[(1 + \xi)[2]_q - 1]^2} + \frac{x(1 + \alpha)}{[[3]_q(1 + \xi[2]_q) - 1]}. \tag{31}$$

3. Fekete-Sezgö Inequality

We introduce the $|a_3 - \mu a_2^2|$ for the function $f(l) \in \mathcal{A}$ in the class $\mathcal{F}_\Sigma^q(x, \alpha, \xi)$ associated with q -Lommel polynomials.

Theorem 3.1. Let $0 < q < 1$ and if the function $f(l)$ given by (1) belongs to $\mathcal{F}_\Sigma^q(x, \alpha, \xi)$ then for any complex μ

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| = k_1(x, \alpha, \xi, q)[((1 - \mu)\varpi(\xi) + \Xi(\xi))m_2 + ((1 - \mu)\varpi(\xi) - \Xi(\xi))n_2].$$

where

$$\varpi(\xi) = \frac{k_1^2(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{\Delta}$$

and

$$\Xi(\xi) = \frac{1}{4[[3]_q(1 + \xi[2]_q) - 1]}.$$

Proof. Using (28), equation (30) becomes,

$$a_3 = A_1(l)(m_2 + n_2) + \frac{k_1(x, \alpha, \xi, q)(m_2 - n_2)}{4[\eta_1 - 1]}, \tag{32}$$

where $\eta_1 = [3]_q(1 + \xi[2]_q)$, $\eta_2 = (1 + \xi)[2]_q$

and

$$A_1(l) = \frac{K_1^3(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{\Delta}$$

and $\Delta = 4K_1^2(x, \alpha, \xi, q)[\eta_1 - \eta_2] - 4(K_2(x, \alpha, \xi, q) - K_1(x, \alpha, \xi, q))[\eta_2 - 1]^2$.

By using (28) and (32), we have

$$a_3 - \mu a_2^2 = [A_1(l) + A_2(l) - A_3(l)]m_2 + [A_1(l) - A_2(l) - A_3(l)]n_2 \tag{33}$$

where

$$A_2(l) = \frac{K_1(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{4[[3]_q(1 + [2]_q) - 1]} ; \quad A_3(l) = \frac{\mu K_1^3(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{\Delta}$$

From (33), we have

$$a_3 - \mu a_2^2 = [(1 - \mu) A_1(l) + A_2(l)] m_2 + [(1 - \mu) A_1(l) - A_2(l)] n_2,$$

hence

$$a_3 - \mu a_2^2 = K_1(x, \alpha, \xi, q) [((1 - \mu)\varpi(\xi) + \Xi(\xi)] m_2 + [((1 - \mu)\varpi(\xi) - \Xi(\xi)] n_2,$$

where

$$\varpi(\xi) = \frac{k_1^2(x, \alpha, \xi, q)}{\Delta}$$

and

$$\Xi(\xi) = \frac{1}{4[[3]_q(1+\xi[2]_q)-1]}.$$

4. Conclusions

We introduce interesting subclass $\mathcal{F}_\Sigma^q(x, \alpha, \xi)$ of bi-univalent function by q -Lommel polynomials. Furthermore, for the recently described subclass, we obtain the Fekete-Szegő functional and initial coefficient bounds.

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